

MICROSTRUCTURE CHARACTERISTIC OF DIRECTIONALLY SOLIDIFIED SI-TASI₂ EUTECTIC *IN SITU* COMPOSITE FOR FIELD EMISSION

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ABSTRACT

Directional solidification of eutectics can produce various kinds of *in situ* composites with self-assembly characteristics, among which the semiconductor-metal eutectic with periodic array of Schottky junctions grown in the composite is to be useful in electronic applications. This paper reports the recent research results about the microstructure characteristic of the directionally solidified Si-TaSi₂ eutectic composite prepared with the electron beam floating zone melting technique. The Si-TaSi₂ eutectic *in situ* composite, which has high-aligned and uniformly distributed TaSi₂ fibres in the Si matrix, is obtained when the solidification rate changes from 0.3mm/min to 6.0mm/min. With the solidification rate increased, the fibre diameter and spacing are all decreased while the fibre density is increased. The TaSi₂ fibre diameter can be less than 1µm, and the fibre spacing is only 2~3µm, while the fibre density can reach 4.2×10⁶ rod/cm². The composite can be preferentially etched to form the cone-shaped TaSi₂ field emission array protruding above the Si matrix.

Keywords: Si-TaSi₂, eutectic *in situ* composite, electron beam floating zone melting, directional solidification, microstructure characteristic

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the preparation of *in situ* composites with self-assembling periodic array of two or more phases by directional solidification of eutectics (DSE) from the melt. DSE has been applied to the metallic [1, 2], semiconductive [3, 4] and ceramic [5, 6] systems to be an alternative way to fabricate the patterned structure with the long-range ordering dimension from the micrometer to nanometer scale. With the matrix and the other phases of the eutectic alloy grown simultaneously from the melt, the directionally solidified eutectic *in situ* composite can be used as structural or functional materials exhibiting various kinds of interesting and excellent properties. The directionally solidified eutectic *in situ* composite can also be processed to be bulk, porous or fiber materials with different dimensionality.

The directionally solidified Si-TaSi₂ is the typical semiconductor-metal eutectic with the TaSi₂ whiskers regularly embedded in the monocrystal Si matrix to form the three-dimensional array of *in situ* Si/TaSi₂ Schottky junctions [3]. With the deep etching technique to remove a depth of Si matrix and to preferentially erode the TaSi₂ fibres into the cone shapes, the TaSi₂ array can be obtained. As TaSi₂ has high melting point, high conductivity, relatively lower work function, better oxidation resistance and native bond strength with silicon, the Si/TaSi₂ Schottky junction has very low junction voltage and high avalanche voltage, which makes it very promising candidate for field emission [3]. On the basis of the former research about the Czochralski-grown Si-TaSi₂ eutectic *in situ* composite [4], this paper reports the recent research results about the microstructure characteristic of the directionally solidified Si-TaSi₂ eutectic composite prepared with the electron beam floating zone melting

(EBFZM) technique.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

In this paper, the Leybold-Heraeus ESZ1.5/5 electron beam floating zone melting furnace is used to prepare the directionally solidified Si-TaSi₂ eutectic *in situ* composite. The sample of 6mm×6mm×30mm is cut from the n-type Czochralski-grown Si-6wt%Ta crystal. The crystal orientation of the silicon matrix is (111). Figure 1 shows the principle of the experiment. With the electron gun mainly consisting of the cathode filament and the focussing system, moving upwards, the sample is zone-melted and directionally solidified. The zone melting rate, which is approximately equal to the solidification rate under steady state growth condition, varies between 0.3~6.0 mm/min. The directionally solidified sample eroded by the HNO₃/HF buffer solution is observed with HITACHI S-570 SEM to reveal the microstructure morphology and phase distribution.

Fig. 1 Schematic diagram of the EBFZM directional solidification

RESULTS

Table 1 gives out the TaSi₂ fibre parameters under different solidification rates. Figure 2 and Figure 3 respectively show the microstructure morphology parallel and vertical to the growth direction at different solidification rate. It can be seen that the Si-TaSi₂ eutectic *in situ* composite, which has high-aligned and uniformly distributed TaSi₂ fibres in the Si matrix, is obtained when the solidification rate changes from 0.3mm/min to 6.0mm/min. With the solidification rate increased, the fibre diameter and spacing are all decreased while the fibre density is increased. Also the fibre distribution is more uniform. When the solidification rate reaches 6.0mm/min, the fibre diameter is reduced to 0.738μm and the fibre spacing is only 2.522μm, while the fibre density reaches 4.202×10⁶ rod/cm² and the fiber volume fraction is 2.011%. This kind of character of TaSi₂ fibre is beneficial to obtain good field emission property for Si-TaSi₂ eutectic composite.

Table 1 Parameters of TaSi₂ fibre under different solidification rates

Solidification rate R (mm/min)	0.3	2.0	3.0	4.0	6.0
Fiber diameter d (μm)	2.164	1.236	1.185	0.834	0.738
Fiber spacing λ (μm)	20.60	12.86	11.23	3.076	2.522
Fiber density Nr (×10 ⁶ rod/cm ²)	0.272	0.698	0.915	3.051	4.202
Fiber volume fraction V (%)	1.000	0.838	1.019	1.667	2.011

Fig. 2 Solidification microstructure morphology of the longitudinal section 25 μ m

(a) $R=0.3\text{mm/min}$ (b) $R=2.0\text{mm/min}$ (c) $R=3.0\text{mm/min}$ (d) $R=4.0\text{mm/min}$ (e) $R=5.0\text{mm/min}$ (f) $R=6.0\text{mm/min}$

Fig. 3 Solidification microstructure morphology of the transversal section 10 μ m

(a) $R=0.3\text{mm/min}$ (b) $R=2.0\text{mm/min}$ (c) $R=3.0\text{mm/min}$ (d) $R=4.0\text{mm/min}$ (e) $R=5.0\text{mm/min}$ (f) $R=6.0\text{mm/min}$

DISCUSSION

Shown as Figure 4(a), the field emission array (FEA), normally fabricated by the semiconductor lithographic technique, is a kind of patterned structure of millions of cold electron emitters, which emits electrons from the tips when subjected to electric field. FEA has become the

basic construction unit of various kinds of vacuum microelectronic devices. Figure 4(b) shows the TaSi₂ array when a depth of Si matrix is removed and the TaSi₂ fibres are preferentially eroded into the cone shapes with the deep etching technique. It can be seen from the comparison of Figure 4(a) and (b) that DSE can be an alternative way to fabricate the patterned structure with self-assembling periodic character although the uniformity and regularity of the array should be further improved.

Fig. 4 Spindt-type field emission array (a) schematic diagram of traditional FEA (b) SEM image of TaSi₂ FEA

EBFZM directional solidification has the following advantages. (1) The energy density of the electron beam is ten thousands times as high as that of the electric arc. (2) Because of the crucibleless and high-vacuum (10^{-5} ~ 10^{-6} mbar) melting, the melt can maintain very high purity. (3) The melting zone is so narrow that the temperature gradient in the melt just in front of the solidification interface can be very large. Glebovsky [7] gave out that the temperature gradient in front of the S/L interface could be 1450 K/cm during the single crystal growth of W by the EBFZM method. (4) The solidification processing can be easily and precisely controlled by adjusting the state of the electron beam such as the strength, the moving rate and the focusing state. Therefore, EBFZM directional solidification is very fit for preparation of the Si-TaSi₂ eutectic *in situ* semiconductor composite for field emission. Moreover, with EBFZM directional solidification the eutectic solidification characteristic under near-rapid solidification rate can be revealed.

CONCLUSION

- [1] With EBFZM directional solidification technique, the Si-TaSi₂ eutectic *in situ* composite, which has high-aligned and uniformly distributed TaSi₂ fibres in the Si matrix, is obtained when the solidification rate changes from 0.3mm/min to 6.0mm/min.
- [2] With the solidification rate increased, the fibre diameter and spacing are all decreased while the fibre density is increased and the fibre distribution is more uniform. When the solidification rate reaches 6.0mm/min, the fibre diameter is reduced to 0.738 μ m and the fibre spacing is only 2.522 μ m, while the fibre density reaches 4.202×10^6 rod/cm² and the fiber volume fraction is 2.011%.
- [3] By the deep etching technique to remove a depth of Si matrix and to preferentially erode the TaSi₂ fibres into the cone shapes, the TaSi₂ field emission array can be obtained.

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